

ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE PROCEDURAL ORDER FOR TERMINATION OF CHARGES

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Abstract. This thesis examines the theoretical and practical dimensions of the institution of termination of charges within the system of criminal procedural law. Particular attention is devoted to the distinct procedural nature of termination of charges, its differences from modification and supplementation of charges, as well as the legal distinctions between complete and partial termination. The findings of the study may contribute to the development of criminal procedural legislation, ensure clarity and uniformity in the application of law, and enhance the efficiency of judicial and investigative practice. The conclusions emphasize the necessity of further developing this institution and underscore the importance of establishing precise normative mechanisms for its application.

Keywords: accusation, termination of charges, dismissal of criminal proceedings, criminal procedural law, rehabilitation, procedural guarantees.

One of the particularly significant directions of accusatory activity is its termination. Although the legislature has regulated the processes of terminating, amending, or supplementing an accusation within a single normative framework, in practice the procedural nature, legal grounds, and legal consequences of terminating an accusation differ substantially from those of amending or supplementing it.

From this perspective, in clarifying the legal content and practical significance of terminating an accusation, some scholars have introduced the concept of “reduction or partial termination of the accusation”. This concept envisages that specific episodes or acts for which the accusation has not been substantiated, certain actions within the accusation that are not confirmed, or instances where excessive qualification has been applied to a set of crimes, may be removed from the accusation¹. Indeed, unlike the amendment of an accusation, in such cases the previously established factual circumstances or legal characterization of the criminal case are not replaced by new ones; rather, the scope of the accusation is reduced, and its volume diminishes.

According to some scholars, partial termination of the accusation represents an independent legal institution, distinct from the complete termination of the criminal case². For example, as noted by the procedural scholar B.B. Murodov, while termination of a criminal case involves the complete conclusion of the case under consideration, the termination of an accusation constitutes a procedural action aimed at annulling the decision to involve an individual as an accused³. Additionally, as noted by D. Kamalkhodjaev, the termination of a criminal case differs from other types of decisions concluding the initial investigation in that it fully resolves the substance of the case and carries final significance⁴. These scholarly views are also supported by us, as the current criminal procedural legislation provides for both full and partial termination of the accusation. At the same time, in cases of partial termination, the criminal case itself is not concluded; rather, only a specific part of the accusation directed against the accused loses its legal effect.

However, it is important to emphasize that the partial termination of an accusation does not, by itself, imply that the involvement of a person as an accused is unlawful or unfounded. Typically, the initial accusation, when first presented by the investigator, does not fully take into account all evidence submitted by the defense. Therefore, partial termination of the accusation does not indicate the absence of legal grounds; rather, it reflects the adjustment of the accusation to its true procedural scope, based on newly identified circumstances and evidence obtained during the investigation of the criminal case.

For this reason, taking this circumstance into account, the legislator did not use the term “partial termination of a criminal case”. Instead, Article 362 of the Criminal Procedure Code emphasizes the concept of “termination of the accusation”, while Article 415 specifically highlights the possibility of removing a part of the accusation or certain descriptive elements of the crime.

When analyzing the grounds for the partial termination of an accusation as stipulated in the second part of Article 362 of the Criminal Procedure Code, it is observed that reference is made to Article 83 of the CPC as “circumstances constituting a basis for the rehabilitation of the accused” and to the first and fifth

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parts of Article 84 as “circumstances preventing the continuation of proceedings”. In our view, the possibility of terminating an accusation is not limited solely to these two grounds. In practice, the circumstances outlined in the first part of Article 362—such as the discovery of new evidence, the identification of ambiguities in the initial accusation, or errors in legal qualification—also provide a legal basis for the partial termination of an accusation.

However, for these circumstances to be sufficient for the termination of charges, they must contain at least one of the procedural grounds stipulated in Article 83 and parts one and five of Article 84 of the Criminal Procedure Code. Otherwise, the decision to terminate the prosecution may be considered legally unfounded and contrary to the principle of legality.

In our view, the grounds established in Articles 83 and 84 of the Criminal Procedure Code possess universal legal significance in practice. These grounds, in accordance with Articles 333, 362, 373, and 381¹¹ of the CPC, simultaneously serve as the legal basis for refusing to initiate criminal proceedings, partially terminating an accusation, or terminating a criminal case entirely. Moreover, the universality of these provisions is evident in that their application is not limited solely to the pre-trial investigation stage but extends to the judicial stages as well. In particular, pursuant to Article 405¹⁰ of the CPC, these grounds are applied during the initial hearing in the first-instance court; during the court session as envisaged by Article 421; and in appellate, cassation, and supervisory proceedings under Article 496, for the annulment of an indictment and termination of a criminal case. As B.B. Murodov emphasizes, the fact that the grounds for refusing to initiate criminal proceedings, partially terminating an accusation, or terminating a criminal case are established within a single provision primarily helps prevent redundancies in legislation and facilitates their practical application⁵.

However, neither the title nor the content of these provisions directly envisage their application as an independent legal basis for partially terminating an accusation. This gives rise to legal ambiguities and divergent interpretations in judicial and investigative practice. Therefore, in our view, it is important from both the perspective of legislative drafting and the uniform application of law to explicitly specify in legislation the applicability of these norms to the partial termination of an accusation.

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Indeed, Article 83 of the Criminal Procedure Code establishes the grounds for declaring a suspect, accused, or defendant innocent and for their rehabilitation. However, in cases of partial termination of the accusation, the individual is not deemed entirely innocent with respect to the criminal case; rather, they are recognized as innocent only in relation to a specific crime or particular episode. This raises an important question: to what extent is it appropriate to apply the grounds set out in Article 83 of the Criminal Procedure Code to the partial termination of an accusation? In such cases, the person is not fully exonerated, and at the conclusion of the proceedings, a conviction or continuation of the accusation for the remaining charges remains possible.

Based on this rationale, it is proposed to supplement Article 83 of the Criminal Procedure Code with the following second paragraph:

“If it is established that a certain part of the accusation or a specific episode of the alleged criminal act did not occur, the criminal elements are absent, or the individual’s involvement in that part of the criminal act is not proven, the person shall be recognized as innocent in respect of that specific part or episode and shall be duly rehabilitated”.

Thus, the above considerations indicate the need to develop an authorial definition of the grounds for terminating an accusation. Accordingly, the grounds for terminating an accusation are circumstances established by criminal procedural legislation, the existence of which renders it legally inadvisable either to fully carry out the procedural activity of the accusation function or to continue it in part, thereby justifying the partial or complete termination of the accusation.

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